

A pipeline for concurrent whole-brain 3D microscopy and MRI in the rat

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Introduction

Diffusion MRI (dMRI) has unique potential for non-invasive mapping of brain connectivity and microstructure; but its measures are indirect, inherently noisy, and of relatively low spatial resolution. As such, optical imaging of post-mortem brain tissue has been used to provide a microstructural gold standard to evaluate, interpret, and validate MRI contrasts[1]. However, comparisons with MRI, which provides 3D images, can be challenging due to the 2D nature of traditional microscopy. Fortunately, advances in tissue clearing techniques[2] and light sheet microscopy[3] have made it possible to optically image larger 3D samples, thereby allowing for optimal MRI- microscopy comparisons in 3D. Whilst previous studies have combined MRI and 3D microscopy in *mice*[4-6], we demonstrate a novel pipeline (Fig 1a) that allows for MRI, whole-brain tissue clearing, and 3D microscopy for the same *rat* brain.

Methods

To optimise ex-vivo MRI acquisition methods (Fig 1b) for the rat, we perfused 5 male Sprague-Dawley rats (Charles River, UK), with (n=3) and without (n=2) gadolinium-based contrast agent (2mM Multihance). Gadolinium reduces the T1 of tissues, allowing for shorter repetition times and faster acquisitions. To ensure our pipeline could handle different data architectures and levels of noise, all samples underwent high-resolution (100/200 μ m isotropic) imaging using 2 preclinical scanners (7T Bruker BioSpec 70/30 or 70/20 USR) with differing hardware (transmit/receive volume coil or surface cryo-coil) and software (PV6 or PV360). Acquisition protocols for multi-shell (b=4000 and b=6000 s/mm²) 90-direction dMRI, were optimised using 2D- and 3D-EPI. We also acquired a T2-weighted 3D-RARE structural scan.

After MRI, the brains were removed from the skull and the hemispheres separated. As the rat brain is 3-4x larger and has a greater lipid content than the mouse, it is significantly more challenging to clear. We overcame these challenges by adopting and optimising the AdipoClear+ protocol[7]. After clearing, the autofluorescence (488nm) of each hemisphere was captured in 3D (Fig 1c) using an Ultrascope II (LaVision Biotec) and InspectorPro (LaVision BioTec). Samples were illuminated from both sides using 3 light sheets and a step size of 10 μ m. Due to the limited field of view available with the x2 objective (MVPLAPO Olympus) at

x0.8 zoom (MXV10 Olympus), the anterior and posterior parts of the brain were imaged separately, with a 30% overlap. The image sets were then fused using Arivis Vision4D (Zeiss) and exported as a tiff stack.

To fully integrate our MRI and microscopy data, we built a multi-modal registration framework using FSL and ANTs. This included conversion and pre-processing of anatomical MRI, dMRI and microscopy data; as well as inhomogeneity and distortion correction; and registration to the SIGMA template[8].

Results

Perfusing samples with gadolinium improved contrast between white and grey matter in the anatomical scans (Fig 1b) and reduced T1 from $\pm 1600\text{ms}$ to $\pm 130\text{ms}$ (data not shown). Furthermore, 3D-EPI yielded significant gains in SNR and CNR, whilst also allowing for shorter scans.

The success of our tissue clearing process and 3D microscopy (Fig 2a) allowed us to observe microstructural details across the whole brain hemisphere and simplified registration to MRI data. Fig. 2b shows that rigid body and affine registration (FLIRT, FSL) aligns the two modalities well, with only marginal gains with non-linear registration (ANTs), which has been the standard for most previous studies that combine histology and MRI[9]. Fig. 2c shows how well our pipeline, which uses non-linear registration, can fuse 3D microscopy images with anatomical and diffusion MRI data.

Conclusions

By providing an end-to-end pipeline for integrating whole-brain 3D microscopy and MRI in the rat, this work paves the way for bridging microscopic information to macroscopic resolution, thereby improving our understanding of dMRI contrasts and what biophysical information they convey.

Figure 1. a) Our end-to-end pipeline for sample preparation, *ex vivo* MRI, tissue clearing, and 3D microscopy, b) Optimisation of *ex vivo* MRI acquisition protocols for the rat brain, and c) Fast volumetric imaging of intrinsic contrast (i.e., autofluorescence) in a cleared brain hemisphere using 3D light sheet microscopy.

Figure 2. a) Mapping 3D microscopic (4 μ m) light sheet images to macroscopic (200 μ m) diffusion MRI data acquired in the same rat brain. b) Aligning microscopy images to anatomical MRI data with rigid body, affine, and non-linear registration (FLIRT, FSL and ANTs). c) Fusion of our microscopy (L) and MRI (R) datasets demonstrates high anatomical correspondence.

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